

THE DARI LANGUAGE AND WORD FORMATION ISSUES IN IRANIAN STUDIES

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Abstract. *In world linguistics, the Dari language is not as extensively studied as other languages such as Persian and Tajik. In Iranistics, the scientific description of this language is primarily characterized by its differences from the modern Persian language. In the field of word formation in Dari, particular emphasis is placed on affixal word formation of parts of speech. In recent years, there has been a notable comprehensive development of Dari language, with tangible changes occurring in all its areas over time. This study shows how Dari language is formed, developed, and improved the causes, regularities, and possibilities of this process, as well as the definition of the principles of word formation are becoming increasingly important. In turn, it highlights the necessity of conducting a separate study of Dari language based on its materials.*

The article presents the processes of word formation in Dari language. The position and function of affixal, semi-affixal word formation, and word formation transposition in the evolution of Dari lexicon are demonstrated through an examination of its intrinsic capabilities.

Keywords: *Dari, Farsi, Farsi-Kabuli, Tajik, word-formation, affixation, semi-affixation, composition, lexicalization, transposition, complex word, derived word.*

Dari language (دري *dar(r)i*), also known in scientific literature as “Farsi” [12:4], “Farsi-Kabuli” [9:6; 10:337-450] or “Kābulī Persian” [39:1-123]) is related to modern Persian and Tajik in terms of language structure. The genesis and most important stages of the historical development of these languages coincide completely, as do the most important monuments of their writing [16:10].

In the 1930s-1950s, several works first highlighted the differences between Dari and modern Persian and similarities with Tajik [39:1-123; 40:117-186]. It demonstrated that modern Persian, Dari, and Tajik are the outcomes of the subsequent evolution of the so-called language of the classical era, namely New Persian, which existed in the territories of Central Asia, Iran, Khorasan, Balkh, and partly India between the 8th and 16th centuries. Furthermore, it was established that the language of classical Persian-Tajik literature up to the 15th and 16th centuries was generally identical across all these areas [5:38; 6:80-85].

The difference between these languages commenced in the 16th century, particularly in the latter part of the century, when the prerequisites for the formation of Persian and Tajik languages, as well as one of the state languages of Afghanistan, gradually emerged [24:125].

Subsequently, because of the study of the language of certain historical and literary monuments and medieval dictionaries, significant corrections were made to this issue. The works of A.K.Arends, L.P.Smirnova, G.I.Kozlov, V.A.Kapranov, M.F.Fazylov, A.Tagirjanov, and especially the consolidated work of the French Iranist J.Lazar have demonstrated the existence of a certain differentiation in the language of early Persian prose of the classical period, as well as the potential for the localization of certain medieval monuments on linguistic grounds. In the field of lexicology, a concise review by A.Z.Rosenfeld included a comparative study of the lexicon of Tajik and Persian languages. The terminological dictionary of S.Byalkovsky, which included

“Afghan” military, and political vocabulary, and the inclusion in the first edition of the “Persian-Russian Dictionary” by B.V. Miller represents the inaugural attempt to study Dari lexicon. It was prepared by M.G.Aslanov and comprises over 2,000 words drawn from a range of socio-political, administrative, military, household, and other domains. The Dari-Russian Dictionary, prepared in co-authorship by L.N.Kiseleva and V.I.Mikolaychik, represents the inaugural edition to be devoted to Dari language in its independent capacity [38:32-48].

The study of Dari vocabulary commenced in Afghanistan during the 1960s. Before this, Dari and Persian were regarded as national variants, with the distinction between them attributed to the perceived lack of literacy among Afghan authors [41]. In the past, the Afghan education system employed the use of Persian grammar and textbooks published in Iran. In 1965, authoritative editions of “مقدمه یی بر دستور زبان” (“Introduction to the Study of Grammar”) [43] and “فونیم شناسی دری” (“Phonemics of Dari Language”) [44] by Mukhammad Rakhim Ilkham were published. Based on Dari language material, the aforementioned resources were prepared.

In 1969, Mukhammad Nasim Neghat Saidi’s book Grammar of Modern Dari Language (“Dastour-e Ma’asir-e Zaban-e Dari”) [46] was published, marking the inaugural significant phase in the investigation of Dari language, not only within Afghanistan but also abroad. In this instance, the focus was not on the language of classical poetry, but rather on the modern literary, written, and spoken Dari language. To this end, samples of modern Dari prose were provided, along with materials from the Afghan press and radio, which served as illustrative examples. This realistic approach to language represented a pivotal shift in the field of Afghan linguistics. In general, M.N.Neghat Saidi’s study addresses many aspects of the grammatical structure of Dari, with a particular focus on syntax, verb forms, and the system of word formation.

The 1960s to the 1990s in Russia saw Dari (Kabuli) language studied in theoretical terms. The studies include scientific works such as the monograph and scientific articles by L.N. Dorofeeva (Kiseleva) [9; 15; 16], phonology and morphology by B.Y. Ostrovsky [21], the vowel system in Kabuli by T. N. Pakhalina [22; 23], phonetics of Dari language by K.I. Polyakov [27], lexicology and phraseology of Dari language by A.F. Baryshnikov [3], studies the grammatical structure of Dari language by V.I. Mikolaychik [18] and others.

In the period of the former Soviet Union, studies were conducted in several areas related to the formation of terms and the replenishment of the vocabulary of Dari language. These included the assimilation of borrowings in Dari by H.Khashimbekov [14], the formation of terminology and the regularities of the process of borrowing in the works of Uzbek scientists H.U.Uralov [31] and A.Z.Shakirov [30]. It would be remiss not to mention the study conducted by V.A.Efimov [11], which focused on the distinctive characteristics of the Khazar dialect in Afghanistan. Additionally, the scientific work of U.Obidov [20] on the Jabal us-Siraj dialect is worthy of note.

No separate study on word formation in Dari language was conducted. In some monographs, in particular those authored by L.N.Kiseleva, R.Farkhadi and M.N.Neghat Saidi [9:22-32; 15:104-130; 16:45-50; 41, 12:150-187; 46:94-172], one can find information about word formation in Dari language. It is noteworthy that the theoretical studies in this field by L.N.Kiseleva (Dorofeeva) and R. Farkhadi, published almost half a century ago, remain of great importance in the scientific community. In particular, the monograph by L.N.Kiseleva devotes special attention to a comparative study of Dari language lexicon with the vocabularies of Persian and Tajik, as well as offering some insights into word formation in Dari [15:104-130]. In turn, researchers R. Farkhadi devotes his study to word formation of names in the Kabuli dialect

[12:150-187], and M.N.Neghat Saidi studies word formation affixes in different parts of speech of Dari language [46:149-159].

In the initial stage of the investigation, H.U.Uralov [32] and then V.V.Belokon [4] examined borrowings in the modern Dari language, focusing on scientific-technical, military, and military-technical terms.

A review of research on Dari language reveals the following types of word formation: affixation, composition, lexicalization, and the semantic method [16:45; 34; 35; 37:35-47]. Affixal word formation and composition were considered as the main types. Furthermore, the affixal type, along with others, is regarded as the most extensively researched [46]. L.N.Kiseleva identifies 103 distinct word-forming and form-forming affixes in Dari language, representing the majority of all such affixes. This list also encompasses productive semi-affixes [15:131-140]. The productivity of these affixal morphemes is not uniform. The formation of nouns and adjectives is most frequently achieved by using affixal word formation. The affixal method of word formation, exemplified by the combination of a *word-forming base and an affixal morpheme* or an *affixal morpheme and a word-forming base*, represents a fundamental and enduring model in the history of the language, Fârsi-ye Dari or Dari [26:70]. In her analysis of eight word-forming suffixes (e.g., *-gak(-ak)*, *-a*, *-i*, *-ih*, *yâ-e nesbat*, *-in* and *-ina*, *-dâni*, *-bâb*, *-ôk*), L.N.Kiseleva elucidates the divergences in the system of word-formation of modern Dari, Persian, and Tajik languages following the classical era [15:111-130]. The aforementioned suffixes are employed in the formation of names denoting a subject, an abstract name, and an adjective name.

Word-forming affixes are presented in M.N.Neghat Saidi's دستور زبان معاصر دری ("Grammar of the Modern Dari Language"), which is devoted to the grammatical structure of Dari language [46:149-159]. In the section of word-forming prefixes (پیشوندهای اشتقاقی اسمی، صفتی) (*pêšwandhâ-ye ešteqâqi-ye esmi, sefati*), 8 prefixes are given. Of these به *ba-*, نا *nâ-*, با *bâ-*, بی *bê-*, نه *na-*, دش *doš-* – adjective-noun, هم *ham-* – noun-adjective-noun, ام *em-* – noun-adjective-adverb. However, in Modern Dari (as in Persian and Tajik) the affixes ام *em-* and دش *doš-* are unproductive, and word formation with their participation is not observed. Word-forming suffixes are classified into groups forming nouns (پسوندهای اسمی *paswandhâ-ye esmi*), adjectives (پسوندهای صفتی *paswandhâ-ye sefati*), adverbs (پسوندهای قیدی *paswandhâ-ye qaidi*) and noun-adjective-adverbs (پسوندهای اسمی - صفتی - قیدی *paswandhâ-ye esmi - sefati - qaidi*). A total of 28 suffixes are used for the formation of nouns, 17 for adjectives, and 8 for adverbs. The function of plural and diminutive affixes is to form words. The suffix چی *-či*, which forms the names of people, is incorrectly classified as an adjective suffix. It is our contention that a number of the 14 suffixes in the category of 'common' affixes forming noun-adjective-adverb-adverb should have been specifically designated as noun suffixes (e.g. بان *-bân* / وان *-wân*) or adjective suffixes (مند *-â*, مند *-mand*). In general, an analysis of the suffixes included in this group reveals some divergence in terms of the fact that the suffixes اسا *-asâ* and سان *-sân* form adjectives and adverbs, respectively. The suffix ا *-a* is most frequently employed in the formation of nouns and adjectives. In conjunction with suffixes denoting the actor, such as گر *-gar*, گار *-gâr*, and کار *-kâr*, it can also give rise to adjectives.

In the field of Persian linguistics, the inability to delineate a clear formal boundary between certain parts of speech has been repeatedly substantiated. This pertains, for instance, to the distinction between nouns and adjectives, as well as between qualitative adjectives and adverbs [19:21-28]. This conclusion is primarily derived from an analysis of non-derivative root words.

In Dari (as in Persian), derivational words in most cases clearly show their belonging to certain lexico-grammatical classes: زیر *zêr* ‘low’ (noun) and ‘lower’ (adjective), but زیرین *zêrin* ‘lower’ (adjective), خنک *xonok* ‘cold’ (adjective) and ‘cold’, ‘cold’ (noun), but خنکی *xonoki* ‘cold’, ‘cold’ (noun), قیمت *qimat* ‘value’, ‘price’, ‘worth’ (noun) and ‘valuable’ (adjective), but پرقیمت *porqimat* ‘valuable’ (adjective), بامداد *bâmdâd* ‘dawn (morning)’, ‘morning dawn’ (noun) and ‘morning’ (adverb), but بامدادان *bâmdâdân* ‘morning’, ‘in the morning’ (adverb) or from نیک *nêk* ‘good, well’ (adjective, adverb) by the suffix *-i* - نیکی *nêki* ‘good’ (noun), from the word تند *tond* ‘hard’, ‘rough’, ‘tough’ (adjective, adverb) by *ba-* and *-i* - بتندی *batondi* ‘rough’, ‘bold’ (adverb).

Thus, the word-forming affix in Dari produces a word that belongs to a certain lexico-grammatical category: in the derived words, the word-forming features are at the same time categorical [15:109].

The most significant contribution to the expansion of the modern Dari vocabulary is the formation of words through the use of semi-affixes, both nominal and verbal. In Dari language, a considerable proportion of word formation characterized by the incorporation of a verb as the second part, which may be the present base of simple verbs, their variants with the suffix *-i* or the negation particle, or the form of the imperative mood. In contrast, the present bases of prefixal and compound verbs are relatively uncommon. Given the considerable number of verb word morphemes, semi-affixation, in addition to affixation and collocation, represents the most productive approach within the system of word formation. The primary function of semi-affixes is the formation of new socio-political and scientific-technical terms. In the field of Iranian studies, research has been conducted on the use of semi-affixes. See also S.A.Aliev, V.I.Mesamed [2; 17] and others. V.I.Mesamed, noting the proximity of semi-affixed words to complex lexical items, refers to them as “compositoids” [17:10]. In L.N.Kiseleva’s classification, semi-affixes are also examined as a constituent of a compound word [16:45-46]. On occasion, semi-affixes are regarded as مرزی میان موارد *mavâred miyân-e marzi*, which may be translated as an ‘intermediate state’ between an independent word and an affix [45:24-25,145]. However, the focus of research on semi-affixes has varied depending on the period under consideration, reflecting a relative and evolving perspective in this field of study.

Many scholars have contributed to this field, including L.N.Kiseleva, R.Farkhadi, M.N.Neghat Saidi [15; 16; 12; 46] in Dari, and the works of V.S.Rastorgueva, N.A.Akhmedjanova, M.Shaki, J.S.Giunashvili, T.D.Chkheidze, Y.A.Rubinichik, L.S.Peysikov, and T.A.Chavchavadze [28; 1; 42; 13; 8; 29; 25; 26; 7] represent a significant contribution to the field of Persian linguistics, particularly in terms of the study of word formation at various levels.

M.N.Neghat Saidi defines a compound word as ‘formed from two independent words or from two independent words and one or more non-self (suffixes, conjunctions, prepositions) parts’ [46:165] and identifies the following types of compound words in Dari language: 1) مرکب امتزاجی *morakkab-e emtezâji* ‘mixed compound words’; 2) مرکب تکراری *morakkab-e takrâri* ‘repeated compound words’; 3) مرکب عطفی *morakkab-e atfi* ‘linked compound words’; 4) مرکب هموزن *morakkab-e hamwazn* ‘compound words with the same (equal) morpheme’; 5) مرکب اتصالی *morakkab-e ettesâli* ‘adjoining compound words’ [46:166-173].

The distinctive features of compound words in Dari language are as follows: 1) phonetic (a compound word has one main accent); 2) grammatical (no grammatical connection between the parts of a compound word); 3) semantic (a compound word expresses one meaning). Of these

features, the main one that allows a compound word to be distinguished from a word combination is the grammatical feature.

In the formation of words, the index of the lexicalization method, namely the transformation of combinations with conjunction into complex words, is relatively high. The process of lexicalisation of word combinations in Dari is still in its infancy, which lends support to the assertion that the boundary between a compound word and a word combination is highly contingent.

Following an in-depth study of the regularities and possibilities of replenishing the lexicon through word formation based on internal resources in Dari language, the following scientific and theoretical conclusions have been reached:

1. In the field of Iranian studies, the distinction between word formation and morphology was first made as a discrete area of study in the 1970s. About Dari language, the processes of word formation and associated phenomena were documented in the lexicology section as annotations about word formation. This situation can be attributed to two factors: a) the study of Dari language commenced in the 1960s, specifically from the moment of the official proclamation of 'Farsi-Kabuli' as 'Dari' in the Constitution of Afghanistan in 1964; b) the existence of the view that Dari language is a national (regional) variant of Persian language.

2. The concurrent usage of two, and in some regions, three languages as official languages has resulted in the population of Afghanistan exhibiting bilingualism and multilingualism. This ethnolinguistic situation has a significant impact on the structural and functional changes and their development in the system of word formation in Dari language.

3. In the context of word formation in Dari and Persian, the affix that forms words simultaneously fulfills the function of a categorical feature.

4. It is evident that the relationship between Dari and Persian will continue to face significant challenges in the future. These include the shared basic vocabulary of the two languages, the discrepancies in the recognition of Dari literary norms by Afghan intellectuals, the considerable number of Persian speakers, the advanced state of the Iranian press, the extensive distribution of Iranian periodicals and non-periodicals in Afghanistan, the Afghan youth educated in Iranian educational institutions, and the activities of Afghan emigrants from Iran in Afghanistan.

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